
IMMERSIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN MEDICAL EDUCATION.

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Abstract.

The article reveals immersiveness, which is understood by the authors as a special teaching method based on immersion in an artificially simulated reality, including elements of relaxation, suggestion and games. There are two types of immersive technologies - VR (virtual reality) and AR (augmented reality). An immersive approach in vocational education is defined as a set of techniques and methods for organizing the interaction of participants in the educational process in a virtual learning environment that provides interactive learning through sensory multi-vector impact on medical students.

Key words.

Immersiveness, relaxation, virtual reality, augmented reality, interactivity, multivector.

Immersive technologies are one of the key levers for changing educational methods and content in schools and universities in many countries of the world [1, p. 83]. The word “immersive” itself has an English etymology and is defined in English dictionaries as “providing, involving or characterized by deep absorption or immersion in something (for example, in an activity, in a real or artificial environment)” [2]. In the context of pedagogical science, immersiveness is interpreted as a special teaching method with elements of relaxation, suggestion and play, based on immersion in an artificially simulated reality. We agree with A.I. Sosnilo and N.N. Rezvanov: immersive teaching aids differ from standard ones, first of all, in that in the traditional pedagogical paradigm, the assimilation of new knowledge occurs through informing and persuading, while immersiveness involves learning through informing and suggestion [1, p. 84]. Immersive technologies, thus, implement the simulation of full or partial immersion in a given environment, alternative space, while changing the channels of interaction with the user.

The advantages of using immersive tools in vocational education are highlighted: activities in an environment as close as possible to the real professional

environment of the future specialist, strengthening the sensory capabilities of the student, increasing motivation to study. Among the promising sectors for the implementation of virtual and augmented reality, the following are noted: technical specialties, specialties of a chemical and biological profile, the transport sector, medicine, and the army. The following barriers to the introduction of immersive technologies have been identified: the need for special training of teaching staff, the possibility of a discrepancy between the actual level of objective competence and the subjective assessment of the capabilities of students, and the increase in psychological, physical, and somatic risks. [3]

Initially, all of the above technologies in the vast majority of cases took place in the gaming industry, but subsequently the scope of their application has expanded significantly: immersiveness has become characteristic of such areas as medicine, industry, advertising, the army, etc. This article leads to the conclusion that it is also advisable to use immersive tools in teaching various types of professional activities.

The implementation of virtual reality tools in the field of vocational education is quite "seamlessly" integrated into the constructivist approach to learning, according to which the student does not just use the tools and learning environments prepared for him, but builds ideas about the environment in which he will have to act, and about the tasks that he to be decided directly in the learning process [4, p. 91]. Taking into account the active influence of immersive technologies on the transformation of learning processes, we define an immersive educational environment as a specially organized environment in which immersive technologies are the leading tool for organizing educational and cognitive activities. It is impossible to imagine the educational environment without classes, in which, like in a mirror, the tools and technologies that implement the tasks are reflected. In modern methodological literature, it is difficult to find lesson developments in which it would be possible to evaluate the role of immersive tools in learning, as well as their place in the content and structure of classes.

The problem of developing learning models using immersive technologies lies not only in determining its structural elements, but also in analyzing the conditions in which it can be implemented. Among the most common VR technologies that can be used by a teacher, the construction and application of QR- codes. It allows you to organize individual and group work both at the seminar and after it. Medical students can use their own smartphones and tablets during various practical tasks.

No less significant technology is implemented by another tool - the HP Reveal application. With its help, auras of images are formed. When you hover your

smartphone screen over them, virtual objects are shown. This happens due to the phone's camera, GPS, accelerometer and other means of identifying objects.

We must not forget that the learning process will be effective if it is provided in a meaningful, methodological and technological way. This means that a classroom that uses immersive technology or creates virtual objects must be equipped accordingly. We are talking about VR helmets, panoramic cameras, software, a library of ready-made virtual models, etc. Modern technologies make it possible to reduce the number of errors, improve the quality of training of specialists, primarily surgeons, through deep immersion in a virtual environment for practicing actions during complex operations/manipulations.

The most interesting and promising solution in the field of medical training is modern VR simulators for surgeons.

The simulator immerses the young specialist in a virtual environment, where he will perform the operation in conditions that are as close to real as possible. Firstly, the technology makes it possible to get used to the situation in the operating room, to work with patients (virtual in this case), whose organisms will react in real time to all manipulations. Fortunately, here a doctor's mistake can become fatal only for a virtual character, and not a real one.

Secondly, the same operations can be practiced over and over again with different scenarios, possible complications, and even in a group. The simulation can contain the full complement of specialists who will be present on the real operation, including assistants and assistants, so that they can work out not only their part of the task, but also the interaction with others.

Thirdly, technology allows both students and beginners to be trained, as well as experienced practicing surgeons who want to learn how to work with new equipment or hone their existing skills to the ideal.

In addition, such systems have analytical capabilities. The quality of the operation performed can be assessed by both the teacher and the program in automatic mode, and the entire procedure can be recorded from the points of the participants in the operation for further evaluation and search for errors.

AR applications are being created that allow, when pointing the camera of a smartphone or tablet, to see the location of organs and veins with detailed background information. In addition, solutions using augmented reality technology can provide up-to-date data and tips on working with complex equipment, including laboratory ones. [9]

In the context of a deep transformation of education, it is impossible not to take into account the serious processes of updating the content and technologies

studied in the course of informatics. In this regard, new approaches are needed to expand and deepen knowledge in this subject area. One of them is the formation of applied competencies necessary for a student who will have to live and work in a completely different socio-cultural and educational environment.

In general, there are several fundamental reasons for expanding the use of virtual and augmented reality technologies in the educational process:

Advantages in mastering educational material

1. The conducted experiments show greater satisfaction of students from the use of technology, better comprehensibility, involvement and other characteristics of the educational process.

2. Growth in the number of implemented projects and software products based on VR. The number of implemented projects and created products has exceeded several thousand and continues to grow.

3. Reduced prices for VR helmets.

4. Successful application of immersive technologies for educational purposes in business.
5. Investment in VR.

6. Cases of successful application of VR in education.

To form an immersive environment, it is important for a modern teacher not only to use modern equipment, but also to model educational processes, apply new methodological approaches and strategies. Conclusion: the introduction of virtual workshop technology into the professional and educational space is associated with a number of objective difficulties, but this should not stop developers and researchers. The process of digitalization all over the world is in full swing, and the faster the scientific community responds to the problems on the way to the development and implementation of educational technologies of the future, the better we can respond to the challenges of global digital industrialization.

Incarceration: the introduction of virtual workshop technology into the professional and educational space is associated with a number of objective difficulties, but this should not stop developers and researchers. The process of digitalization all over the world is in full swing, and the faster the scientific community responds to the problems on the way to the development and implementation of educational technologies of the future, the better we can respond to the challenges of global digital industrialization.

Conclusions: Analyzing the specifics of the use of immersive technologies by modern media, we can conclude that these innovations are actively developing in the modern information and communication space. Augmented reality is widely used today in medicine, psychology, design (and art in general), and construction.

The use of AR/VR technologies in medical education provides a significant increase in student interest. They are 2.9 times more proactive and attentive when working with modern visualization and demonstration systems, which has a very positive effect on the assimilation of information, the amount of knowledge acquired during their studies and, of course, on the qualifications of a young specialist.

With AR/VR, you can significantly improve the quality of medicine, reduce the number of medical errors and increase patient comfort. The potential of all forms of artificial reality is enormous. However, due to the limited scope, as well as the presence of a number of technical obstacles to the consumption of content by users, the development of AR and VR is not a priority for news resources. For this reason, the use of these technologies in medical education is relevant. But, as studies and practice show, the consumer is already ready for this type of content, so its progressive development and distribution is natural. Further expansion of scientific understanding of immersive technology in medicine will contribute to the effective use of these technologies in media practice.

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